

MONITORING AND EVALUATION PRACTICES AND PERFORMANCE OF NATIONAL POLICE SERVICE IN MERU COUNTY

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Abstract: The National Police Service came into effect through enactment of National Police Service Act 2017 from which the Service also derives its mandate. It can be argued that an accountable, transparent and efficient Policing Service is a requirement to safety and comfort of all communities in Kenya. To ensure that Police meet their objectives while executing their duties and serving the public, large public resources have been committed to ensure that the Service meets the up to date modern status. Much progress has been made through creation of the National Police Service, the National Police Service Commission, and other oversight bodies such as the Internal Affairs Unit and the Independent Policing Oversight Authority that oversee the performance of the Police. The general objective of the study was to determine the role of Monitoring and Evaluation practices and performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. Specific Objectives was to examine the role of stakeholder engagement on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County, to determine the role of resource allocation on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County, to determine the role of data management on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County, to determine the role of capacity building on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Police Stations in the entire Meru County will be used in this project. This study adopted descriptive survey design. The target population was 312 respondents from which a sample size of 175 respondents was drawn. SPSS was used for data analysis. A pilot study was conducted where 10% of sample was administered with questionnaires. SPSS (25) was used to check on reliability and validity of the research instrument. The pilot study revealed that the variables had Cronbach alpha coefficients of greater than 0.7 and thus, they were reliable. Construct validity was checked using Factor analysis where items with factor loading below 0.5 were excluded from further analysis. The study analysis conducted both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that monitoring and evaluation practices affected performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. The final study revealed that stakeholder involvement to have a positive and significant role on performance of National Police Service in Meru County. The study found that resource allocation to have a positive and significant role on performance of National Police Service. The study also found data management to have a positive and significant role on performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Finally, the study found capacity building to have a positive and significant role on performance of National Police Service in Meru County. The study recommends the use of monitoring and evaluation practices to ensure improvement of performance in the National Police Service in Meru County. Monitoring and evaluation practices explained 84.8% change of performance in the National Police Service in Meru County. The study will be useful to decision makers, the public, and the National Police service.

Keyword: Monitoring and Evaluation Practices, National Police Service, Resource Management, Stakeholder engagement, Meru County.

I. INTRODUCTION

The National Police Service Act of 2017 establishes the power of the National Police Service (NPS) [1]. Accountability, openness, and efficacy, among other qualities, are essential for the National Police Service's proper operationalization in providing Services to Kenyans. Members of the National Police Service have adopted reform that acts as one of the largest and most difficult public sector restructures similar to devolution in carrying out their mandate. Large public resources have

been devoted to the modernization of the Kenyan Police Service, and much progress has been made, including the creation of the National Police Service, the National Police Service Commission (NPSC), and other oversight bodies such as the Internal Affairs Unit and the Independent Policing Oversight Authority, which oversee the performance of the Police [2]. Apart from overseeing operations of the Police, such institutions also make policies and regulations including appointments, recruitments, promotions, discipline, community policing, transfers and deployments among others [3].

There are social conditions in which the Police *modus operandi* has changed over a period of time. Aspects of globalization, diversity in rural-urban migration, emergence of the mobile phone, internet and social media, growing youth population, fragmentation of traditional communities, increasing levels of poverty and inequality, radicalization of citizens and terror attacks in the country have all impacted the way Police execute their duties. Nevertheless, policing in Kenya continues to take place in diverse and contrasting manner. In pre-colonial times, majority of states and societies in sub-Saharan Africa did not have professional full-time law enforcement organs and in many situations centralized rulers only relied on small groupings of armed men whom they were using in law enforcement and making crucial judicial decisions in the society. Mostly laws and rules governing the societal social settings were communicated orally through selected elders since the population then lacked ability to write scripts. This however changed in the 19th century during scramble and partition of Africa as European colonialists introduced written laws that governed policing work in the colonies that they had absolute power over [4].

In the 1920's and 1930s most European colonies started experiencing gradual changes socially and economically and indirect form of leadership that had been bestowed on traditional rulers and colonial Police officers in Africa started experiencing a sharp turn towards formation of law enforcement organizations that were professional in their work. New methods of curbing crime and maintaining law and order such as scientific methods of fingerprinting, documenting crime scenes, forensics analysis of crimes were advocated as educated officers were introduced in the system. This however, did not eliminate all challenges in Policing work since almost all the Police units were advocates of an oppressive and exploitative system put in place by the colonialists. Colonial militaries, colonial Police forces practiced and implemented racial hierarchy of leadership where the minority white Europeans were superiors and black Africans who were majority formed the lower ranks. Working conditions in the Police force then were not different either. Vital and essential Services like salaries, accommodation, food, stores among others were drawn towards racial lines. Besides, African Police officers were usually recruited from few marginalized communities perceived by colonialists as traditional martial tribes and those that were collaborators [4].

Radical changes were experienced in the 1950's and 1960's as the colonial Police forces experienced transformation to the National Police forces of new independent states. During this period, many European Police officers controlled policing work but with time, it transitioned to African Police leadership and Africans who were in the Police force started enjoying the new command structure that was not based on racial status. The early colonial Police officers were mostly militarized armies, which used all forms of violence to oppress citizens unlike the current Police Service that is professional and guided by the rule of law [3]. The Imperial British East Africa (I.B.E.A.) Company was utilized by Sir William McKinnon to defend his business enterprises along the Kenyan coast, and the country's governance under the Police can be said to have had a humble beginning in the years 1887 to 1902. In Mombasa, Sir William McKinnon's efforts resulted in the formation of a true Police force. During this time, policing activity was primarily focused on defending the I.B.E.A. Company's business, and the work force was primarily made up of Indians, with only a few Africans, known locally as "Askaris," being eligible to join the Police force [4]. Construction of Kenya - Uganda Railway by the Europeans saw growth of Police force and by 1902 there were Police Service units at Mombasa, Nairobi and Kisumu. Their main mandate was protecting the railways property, materials used in construction and the people who were constructing the railway line.

A change over time and advancement of crime in 1920's led to formation of Criminal Intelligence Unit (CIU) which was responsible for collecting, tabulating and recording history and data of criminals in the Country. As of now, Kenya Police is a public body that authorizes law in the Country and includes many arms inside its positions that guarantees that Law and order are kept. Each arm reports to a County Police Commander, which thus divides its power by local Police Divisions headquartered at local Police stations and divisions who then, at that point, report to Kenya Police Headquarters in Nairobi. The 2016 Constitution saw rebranding of the Kenya Police Service and the Administration Police to National Police Service. The Service is now bigger than before and the population of Police Officers has grown from 44,000 to 89,000 while the number of Police Stations has grown from 340 to 547 [5].

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Today policing in Kenya takes place in an economic, social, and political context that has radically changed since 2018, when reforms began and the subject of policing dominates public debate. All Kenyans should enjoy a secure and habitable environment as Police strive to maintain law and order. The National Police Service is responsible for ensuring that theft, acts of violence, disturbances of the peace, and the execution of criminal law penalties are handled in line with the law [5]. Police officers in the National Police Service are always not perfect while executing their duties hence various incidences of human rights abuses among the members of public have been witnessed. It can be noted that Kenyan Police officers are among the poorly paid employees in the country and have to make cope with archaic housing facilities that has not been expanded or renovated since the 1970s, a factor that has made them prone to corruption and crime. Extorting the public and bribery are common practices and the Kenyan people rank the Police among the most corrupt government organs in the country. According [6] the level of bribery increased by 11% in the years 2016 however, formation of Independent bodies and Commissions by the National government have ensured that there are been checks and balances in the National Police [5]. In 2018, 17,062 cases relating to criminal activities were reported in Eastern region with Meru County leading in crime at 5,689 cases or 34% [5].

In particular, Meru County tops Eastern Province in terms of Crime rate. In 2018, 17,062 cases relating to criminal activities were reported in Eastern region with Meru County leading in crime at 5,689 cases or 34% [5]. In the year 2020 Eastern region was third in the country recording 13,532 cases, with Meru County leading in terms of crimes reported to police at 4,163 cases or 6%. [7]. Various studies have been conducted on the influence of monitoring and evaluation planning aspects on performance of National Police Service. ;[14] carried a sturdy on the effects of monitoring and evaluation on Change Management in the National Police Service in Nakuru County, and [6] conducted a sturdy on monitoring and evaluation and strategic plans implementation in administration Police Service in Baringo County, Kenya. Nevertheless, none of these studies focused on the role of Monitoring and Evaluation practices and performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. To fill this gap, the current study seeks to examine the role of stakeholder involvement, resource management, data management and organizational learning on performance of National Police Service in Meru County.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to determine the role of Monitoring and Evaluation practices and performance of the National Police Service in Meru County.

Specific Objectives

- i. To examine the role of stakeholder's involvement on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County.
- ii. To determine the role of resource allocation on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study was guided by Stakeholder involvement and Resource Dependence Theory

A. Stakeholder Involvement Theory

Stakeholder engagement is a philosophy of organizational management and corporate ethics that focuses on morals and values in the administration of a company, as well as ensuring the integrity of the decision-making process. This theory defines and models stakeholders in a company, as well as describes and offers techniques for management to take into account their interests. It tries to address the "Principle of Who or What Really Counts" in general [8]. [8] points out that there is need to treat an organization as groups of stakeholders with the main reason being managing their interests, needs and viewpoints. The managers of a given firm must manage the corporations that they head for the benefit of its stakeholders in order to ensure their rights and the participation in decision serve common interest of all stakeholders. This theory will guide the study in establishing the aspects of stakeholder involvement on performance of NPS in Meru County.

B. Resource Allocation Theory

This is whereby an organization determines how best to apportion its factors of production between the various productive activities in which it wishes to engage. It is suggested that none of the academic approaches to date has provided an entirely coherent picture of the process, in part because of the contradictory models of the process that they generate. This theory recognizes that as time goes, developed countries are using their resources to develop undeveloped countries and this is

what the NGO projects are meant to provide to its beneficiaries upon completion of the projects [9]. The study further shows that the developed countries can protect themselves from being turned on by the developing nations, making their system more secure as time goes on more so when it comes to the educational facilities. In describing poverty, [9] indicated that the level of poverty in Sub Sahara is evidence of the developing needs that developed countries tend to bridge. The study borrowed the concept of resource mobilization theory to develop the variable of resource management. This theory will be useful in assessing role of resource allocation on performance of NPS in Meru County.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework sets the stage for the presentation of the particular research question that drives the investigation being reported based on the problem statement.

Figure 1

A. Stakeholder Involvement

Stakeholder engagement is the process by which an organization involves people who may be affected by the decisions it makes or can influence the implementation of its decisions. [10] ascertain Monitoring and Evaluation is vital in stakeholder involvement process of any given organization whether in private or public sector. An underlying principle of stakeholder engagement is that stakeholders have the chance to influence the decision-making process. It is with no doubt that monitoring and evaluation systems support development by generating accurate and timely information that is useful to stake holders. Such information is important to programme managers and stakeholders who require it to make managerial decisions in the top management. This in return improves effectiveness in public participation [11].

B. Resource Management

Resource allocation is another way to speak of resource management or resource scheduling, which is the scheduling of tasks and the associated resources that those tasks require to be completed. Part of resource allocation is knowing the availability of your resources and scheduling them to coincide with your project timeline. When allocating resources, it can be for the project or non-project activities, such as administration, support, operations, etc. These resources can be either fully or partially available, which has to be considered when scheduling resource [12]. As difficult as it might be to allocate resources correctly over the life cycle of a project, it's an essential part of any thorough project management plan and should be done in the planning stage of a project. This helps keep costs down, maximizes productivity and helps with team morale, as well as facilitates client satisfaction by achieving the best outcome and successfully delivering the project. The reasons for target group involvement therefore, include the desire to effect change in individuals, in projects, or organizations, and, in some cases, in society at large, as well as building the capacity of a group or an institution. Besides, the participatory approach also constitutes a learning experience for the project stakeholders, increasing their understanding of the project strategy, and contributing to improved communication between project actors who are working at different levels of project implementation [12]

C. Performance

Performance is said to be completion of a given task while applying knowledge, skills and abilities. In an organization for example performance means good ranking with the hypothesized conception of requirements of a task role [13]. Basically, when dealing with how various institutions perform, it is notable to consider other aspects like performance contracting, stakeholder involvement, customer satisfaction, goals and objectives of that organization since such can be used as indicators to gauge performance.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population included Police Officers from Kenya Police, Directorate of Criminal Investigation and Administration Police Officers in Meru County where the lower cadre i.e. Constables, Non-commissioned Officers and Senior Officers. A total of 312 police officers were targeted. Yamane (1967) formula was used to determine the sample size where 175 sample was obtained. Primary data was collected through administering structured questions. The study adopted a drop and pick method. Descriptive statistics for example mean and a frequency was used to perform data analysis.

V. RESEARCH FINDINGS

A. Descriptive Statistics

The study analyzed the data using descriptive statistics using frequencies, measure of central tendency, and measure of central dispersion. The results per study variables are presented in tables.

i). Stakeholder involvement

The first variable was Stakeholder involvement which aimed at examining the role of stakeholders' involvement on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Table I below shows the descriptive statistics results.

TABLE 1: STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

Statement	Mean	Stdev
The Service's M&E system engages its stakeholders thus they are satisfied on its performance	3.78	1.003
The Service monitors its operations	3.11	1.410
The Service has a monitoring system	3.00	1.372
Decisions from monitoring practice affects stakeholders	2.89	1.451
The institution uses monitoring and evaluation systems	3.11	1.410
The public is involved in some of the activities that are carried out by Police within the County	3.42	1.451
Composite Mean	3.22	1.349

Respondents generally agreed that the Service's M&E system engages its stakeholders thus they are satisfied on its performance supported by the mean of 3.78. There was some slight agreement by respondents that the Service monitors its operations as evident from the mean of 3.11. There is also some slight agreement by the respondents that the Service has a monitoring system (mean = 3.00). Some slight agreement was also found to suggest decisions from monitoring system affect stakeholders as shown by the mean of 2.89. Some slight agreement was found from the respondents that suggest there is a use of monitoring systems by the institution as proven by the mean of 3.11. Respondents slightly agreed that the public is involved in some of the activities that are carried out by Police within the County as proven by the mean of 3.42. The composite mean of 3.42 provide some slight statistical evidence to suggest stakeholder involvement to some extent affect performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Stakeholder engagement is the process by which an organization involves people who may be affected by the decisions it makes or can influence the implementation of its decisions.[10] ascertains that Monitoring and Evaluation is vital in stakeholder involvement process of any given organization whether in private or public sector. An underlying principle of stakeholder engagement is that stakeholders have the chance to influence the decision-making process.

ii). Resource management

The second independent variable was Resource management. The variable aimed at determining the role of resource allocation on practices and performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Table 2 below shows the results.

TABLE II: RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Statement	Mean	Stdev
Availability of adequate resources affects implementation of an organization's strategy	3.83	0.786
The County has enough Police in Meru County	2.78	1.309
The County has adequate workforce to achieve all the plans that have been drafted to execute the ambitious strategies that they come up with	3.11	1.491
Financial resources facilitate project implementation	2.89	1.323
There is shared knowledge between lower-level management and non-management Police in Meru County	3.22	1.003
Composite Mean	3.17	1.182

Availability of adequate resources was slightly found to affect the implementation of an organization’s strategy (3.83). Resource allocation should be undertaken within an organization towards M&E system in a controlled manner to ensure that this does not pose a challenge to the implementation of strategy. [15] opines that lack of adequate resources is an impediment to the success of the M&E system and process thus, the organization should ensure they set aside enough funds to support monitoring and evaluation activities. There was some very slight agreement that the County has enough Police in Meru County (2.78). The County has adequate workforce to achieve all the plans that have been drafted to execute the ambitious strategies that they come up with was slightly agreed by the respondents (3.11). [16] while examining challenges facing implementation of strategic plans in NPS noted that though the Service was over stretched there was inappropriate deployment where a good number of Police officers were undertaking functions which were supposed to be carried out by other people. Resources are of great importance in helping an institution meet its set goals and objectives if well utilized.

Financial resources were slightly found to facilitate project implementation as evident from the mean of 2.89. [17] emphasize the importance of M&E budgeting for efficiency and effectiveness of oversight projects and programs to enhance their performance. The respondents slightly agreed that there is shared knowledge between lower-level management and non-management Police in Meru County as shown by the mean of 3.22. The composite mean of 3.17 provide some slight significance evidence to suggest to some extent resource management as M&E practice influence performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. [18] note that an efficacious project budget is an important role in achieving organization growth and development. Most project managers appreciate that monitoring and evaluation budgeting of projects is important if the project objectives and success is to be achieved. Project monitoring and evaluation exercise adds value to the overall efficiency of project planning, management and implementation by offering corrective action to the variances from the expected standard [19].

iii). Performance of National Police Service

The main objective of the study is to determine the role of Monitoring and Evaluation practices on performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. Table 3 below shows the results.

TABLE III: PERFORMANCE OF NATIONAL POLICE SERVICE

Statement	Mean	Stdev
Response rate	3.94	0.873
Response time	4.06	0.738
Accountability	3.72	1.127
Efficiency	3.50	1.043
Level of satisfaction	3.22	1.003
Composite Mean	3.69	0.957

Respondents generally agreed the response rate of the National Police Service in Meru County was high as supported by the mean of 3.94. Further, the respondents also agreed that the response time by the National Police Service in Meru County was good as supported by the mean of 4.06. Complaint processing speed was at 18% in the year 2016, in 2017% the level of complaint processing speed improved to 22%, in 2018, the level of complaint processing speed was at 24% which slightly increased to 25% in the years 2019 and then increased to 31% in the year 2020. On accountability, the respondents generally agreed that the National Police Service in Meru County were accountable as shown by the mean of 3.72. [20] notes that with adoption of new accountability standards, institutions performance is evidence based. Baselines have been established against which performance is measured. A positive change is attributed to improved performance while negative change may signal some downwards performance.’ However, the study found some slight evidence to suggest the efficiency of the National Police Service in Meru County as shown by the mean of 3.50. [21] describes performance as the ability to contribute the employment and wealth creation through the initiating, growth and sustainability of an oversight. Respondents also slightly agreed on their satisfaction level by the National Police Service in Meru County.

The composite mean of 3.69 provided some slightly agreement that the performance of National Police Service in Meru County is notable. Performance is said to be completion of a given task while applying knowledge, skills and abilities. In an organization for example performance means good ranking with the hypothesized conception of requirements of a task role [13]. Basically when dealing with how various institutions perform, it is notable to consider other aspects like performance contracting, stakeholder involvement, customer satisfaction, goals and objectives of that organization since such can be used as indicators to gauge performance. In examining organization’s performance, it is important to consider a number of factors such as stakeholders that interact with and within the organization, the heterogeneity of the

organizational resources, environments and strategic choices an institution has adopted as these contributes to attainment of set goals and objectives. These are indicators of variation of institution’s performance over time and aspects through which an institution can measure its performance to inform the next level of action.

B. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on Correlation, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and regression analysis.

i). Correlation

TABLE IV: CORRELATION MATRIX

		PNPS	Stakeholder Involvement	Resource Allocation
Performance of National Police Service	Pearson Correlation	1	.381*	.516*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.041	.032
	N	143	143	143

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

According to the results, there was a weak relationship between stakeholder involvement and the performance of National Police Service in Meru County (r = 0.381, p value =0.041). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.041 was less than 0.05 (significant level). The findings are contrary with Njau (2019)[14] that there exists a statistically significant positive relationship between stakeholder involvement change management in the National Police Service in Nakuru County. Moreover, the results revealed that there was a very strong relationship between resource allocation and the performance of National Police Service in Meru County (r = 0.516, p value =0.032). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.032 was less than 0.05 (significant level). The findings are in line with the findings of [18] who indicated that there is a very strong relationship between monitoring and evaluation budgeting and organization performance.

i). Analysis of Variance

TABLE V: ANOVA RESULTS

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	138.472	4	34.618	18.124	.000 ^b
	Residual	263.58	138	1.9100		
	Total	402.052	142			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of National Police Service

b. Predictors: (Constant), Stakeholder Involvement, Resource Allocation, Data Management, and Capacity Building.

From Table 5 above, F(4, 138) = 18.124, P –value (0.000 < 0.05) further, the F-Statistics (4, 138) is greater than F-Critical (4, 138) = 2.437 and thus , there is significance difference between the means of groups or variation of means. At least one of the predictor variables in Stakeholder Involvement, Resource Allocation, Data Management, and Capacity Building was significant and fit to explain change in performance of National Police Service in Meru County.

ii). Regression Analysis

The study assumed multiple linear relationships between the study constructs, and is expected to follow a general regression model as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon \dots \dots (ii)$$

The regression results are shown on Table 4.6 below.

TABLE VI: REGRESSION RESULTS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	21.384	5.177		4.130	.006
Stakeholder Involvement (SI)	.152	.180	.228	.843	.043
Resource Allocation (RA)	.607	.159	.792	3.820	.009

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of National Police Service in Meru County

From Regression analysis, Stakeholder Involvement p-value (0.043) and Resource Management p-value (0.009), The beta coefficients of the variables were: Stakeholder Involvement ($\beta = 0.152$), and Resource Allocation ($\beta = 0.607$) and the value of the constant was 21.384. According to the results, stakeholder involvement has a significant effect on performance of National Police Service in Meru County ($\beta_1=0.152$, p value= 0.043). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.043 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The findings are in line with the findings of [22] who indicated that there is a very strong relationship between stakeholder involvement and organization performance. The results also revealed that Resource Management has a significant effect on performance of National Police Service in Meru County ($\beta_1=0.607$, p value= 0.009). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.009 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The findings are in line with the findings of [18] who indicated that there is a very strong relationship between monitoring and evaluation budgeting and organization performance.. In conclusion, Resource Allocation had the biggest effect on Performance of National Police Service with a standard beta coefficient of .792 and Stakeholder involvement had the least influence on Performance of National Police Service in Meru County. The model was fitted as follows:

$$\text{Performance of NPS} = 21.384 + 0.152\text{SI} + 0.607\text{RM} \dots\dots\dots(\text{iii})$$

iii). Model Summary

The model summary shows how the rate of independent variables explains the change in dependent variable. The r is used to measure the correlation of the dependent variable (Performance of National Police Service in Meru County) in term of the independent variables (Stakeholder Involvement, Resource Allocation, Data Management, and Capacity Building). The model for the study was summarized as shown in Table VII below.

TABLE VII: MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.921 ^a	.848	.801	0.26881

From the model summary table, the coefficient for determination (R²) is 0.848 or 84.8%. R² is the coefficient for determination which measures the strength of the correlation between Monitoring and Evaluation practices and Performance of National Police Service in Meru County. Thus, Monitoring and Evaluation practices (Stakeholder Involvement, Resource Allocation, Data Management, and Capacity Building) can explain 84.8 % Performance of National Police Service in Meru County. In this study, 15.2% variability in Performance of National Police Service in Meru County is contributed by other Monitoring and Evaluation practices.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Monitoring and Evaluation Practices have a positive and significant role on the performance of National Police Service in Meu County. On the sustainability of Meru County projects. The study found that the National Police Service’s M&E system engages its stakeholders thus they are satisfied on its performance. The study also found that the National Police Service also monitors its operations. Further, the National Police Service has a monitoring system. And finally, the study found the decisions from monitoring system affect stakeholders.

In addition, the study concludes that resource management has positive significant role on the performance of the National Police Service in Meru County. The study found that availability of adequate resources affected the implementation of an organization’s strategy The County has enough Police in Meru County. The County also has adequate workforce to achieve all the plans that have been drafted to execute the ambitious strategies that they come up with. Financial resources facilitate the project implementation. There is shared knowledge between lower-level management and non-management Police in Meru County.

The study recommends that the management of National Police Service should continue ensuring routine monitoring for all organization activities. In addition, the study found that monitoring and evaluation department is not adequately funded. This study therefore recommends that the management of National Police Service should increase budget for the monitoring and evaluation department to enable effectiveness and smooth operations of the Service. Further, study found that the National Police Service M&E department is not adequately staffed and skilled. This study therefore recommends that the management of the National Police Service should formulate and implement effective staff retention programmes to ensure adequacy of employees. Finally, the study therefore suggests further studies on the influence of M&E practices and performance in other organizations in Kenya.

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